

Effect of Spraying with Marvel Nutrient and Antioxidants on the Mineral Content of Apricot leaves Labib Cultivar

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Abstract:

This study was carried out in one of the orchards of Kerbala city/Al-Hussainiya district. Where 30 apricot trees of Labib cultivar were selected, each tree was considered as an independent experimental unit with three replications. Foliar fertilizer by Marvel Nutrient solution at a concentration (0,2) ml/L was the first factor and the second factor was antioxidants which represented by ascorbic acid and citric acid at concentrations (500,1000) mg/L. for each tree. In addition, water was sprayed as the control application. The results showed that there was a significant effect for experimental treatments on the content apricot trees leaves of the mineral

elements (Nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, zinc and iron as the nutrient solution F2 and the antioxidant factor A2, S2 were superior. The interactions between factors F2*A2, F2* S2 (nutrient solution and antioxidants) was greater in giving the highest results levels of the content apricot trees leaves of the mineral elements (NPK, Fe and Zn).

Keywords: *Apricot, Foliar fertilizer, Antioxidants, Nutrient solution.*

Introduction

The Apricot *Prunus armenica* L. belongs to the subfamily Prunoidae, which belongs to the Rosaceae family. Apricot trees are characterized by their rapid growth and fruiting (Bortiri et al.,2001). Apricots are grown in temperate regions such as the Mediterranean countries, America, California in these places there are the greatest apricot farms in the world (Joley et al., 1975). The nutritional importance of apricots is due to their high content of vitamin A and niacin, compared to other fruits, they are also an excellent source of sugar (A.F.G, 2015).

Apricots are grown in Iraq mostly in the central region as well as in the northern region, especially local varieties. It is not possible to plant early varieties in cold regions for fear of

spring freezes because the flowers open up early before vegetative growth (Al-Douri and Al-RAWI,2000).

Feeding the plant with mineral elements greatly affects the quantity of production and the quality of the fruit, as foliar fertilization has a major role in improving the growth of trees through the arrival for macronutrients such as nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium in a way that can be absorbed by the leaves, as sufficient quantities of macronutrients are necessary for plant growth (Obreza et al.,2008). Nitrogen is one of the important and effective elements needed by the plant for it is effective role in the formation of cell protoplasm after water, and its ratio is about 2-4 % of the dry matter of the plant (Havlin et al.,2005).

Phosphorus also has an active role in the vital processes of the plant such as the process of carbon metabolism. The formation and demolition of carbohydrates and transfer of energy within the plant as well as its role in accelerating flowering (Jundia, 2003). Potassium plays a role in many physiological processes within the plant such as transfer of nutrients and salts, the formation of sugars and proteins in addition to cell division (Obreza et al., 2008).

Iron has an effective and essential role in the system of many enzymes involved in the process of respiration, including cytochrome oxidase, peroxidase, catalase, as it is important in transfer of electrons in oxidation and reduction reactions in addition it has a role in the nutritional metabolism of the cell (Al-Muriqi, 2005). It also has an essential role in the representation of amino acids and chloroplasts, as it helps in the construction of chlorophyll, although it does not enter into composition (Taiz & Zeiger, 2002).

Ahmed and Morsy (2001), indicated that treated apricot trees of the Canino cultivar in sandy soils with nutrients, it gave an increase production, especially treating it with boron (Álvarez-Fernández et al., 2003), found that when peach trees were sprayed with iron at a concentration of 300 mg/L and pear trees, the Red variety of both trees containing iron at a rate of 250 mg/L alone or with zinc and manganese may increase leaf chlorophyll content and improve vegetative growth, flowering and fruiting. As for the role of antioxidants in improving of plant growth, ascorbic acid which is one of the antioxidants that have a role in stimulating and energizing the vegetative and fruiting growth for different fruit trees and its effect on the plant is like to effect of growth – active regulators (Johnson et al., 1999, Zulaikha, 2013) indicated that the role of different levels of ascorbic acid (0, 25, 250, 750) mg/L. in the vegetative growth indicators of peach trees Early cultivar, the results showed a significant increase in in the number of flowers.

Citric acid is considered a non-enzymatic antioxidant, it has an effective role as it acts as a scavenger for free radicals resulting from the stresses that the plant is exposed to and which affect the disturbed nutritional transitions, many

of studies and research have indicated the role of citric acid in the growth and production of some plant species, and it was indicated by (Vorobev, 1999) as he showed that foliar spraying with citric acid at a concentration of 300 mg / L on apple trees led to a significant increase in the number of flowers and fruiting branches and production (Ahmed, 2003), showed that the importance of citric acid at a concentration of 2000 ppm in improving the growth characteristics of apple trees, (Anna variety), as it led to an increase in the number of flowers and improvement of fruit quality, and early production. Therefore, the experiment aimed to investigate the role of foliar fertilization by nutrient solution Marvel and Antioxidants in the content of apricot tree leaves from mineral elements.

Materials and Methods

This experiment was conducted on Apricot trees (Labib) in one of the orchards of Karbala Governorate / Al-Husseiniyah District during the growing season (2021-2022). The experiment was conducted on 30 trees, and each tree was treated as an independent experimental unit with three replications. The age of the trees was approximately 15 years old and the trees were in same size as possible all planted by square method at distance (7*7) meter grafted with apricot seed stocks that were reared on balls and were free of diseases. The all tested treatments were sprayed three times in the same trees each tree was sprayed until it reached the point of complete wetness. Before conducting the experiment, some service operations were carried out by removing the bushes, and the trees were distinguished by numbering (transaction numbers) randomly, in addition to washing the trees one day before the spraying process.

The experiment was designed in a randomized completely blocks design with three replicates, each consisted of one tree (RCBD). The statistical differences between the treatments were analyzed using the least significant difference (L.S.D.) at the probability 5%. Fertilizer treatments for foliar spray were prepared according the concentrations under

study, and a spreader (Al-Zahi liquid detergent in the amount 0.1ml / L.) was added. The number of sprays, was 3 sprays from the beginning of March, and the period between one spraying and the other was 20 days. The spraying process was applied in the early morning.

Transaction concentrations and codes for each replicate:

-F1Z0 = (0ml/L. Marvel solution + 0mg/L. antioxidants)

-F1A1 =(0 ml/L.Marvel solution+500 mg/L. ascorbic acid)

-F1S1 =(0 ml/L. Marvel solution + 500 mg/L. citric acid)

-F1A2 =(0 ml /L. Marvel solution + 1000 mg/L. ascorbic acid)

-F1S2= (0ml/L. Marvel solution +1000 mg/L. citric acid)

-F2Z0=(2ml/L. Marvel solution + 0 mg/L. antioxidants)

-F2A1 =(2ml/L.Marvel solution + 500 mg/L. ascorbic acid)

-F2S2 = (2 ml /L. Marvel solution + 500 mg / L. Citric acid)

-F2A2 =(2ml/L. Marvel solution + 1000 mg /L. Ascorbic acid)

-F2S2=(2 ml/L. Marvel solution + 1000 mg/L.citric acid)

Table 1. The Components of Orchard Soil

Sample	pH	E.C	Sand	Silt	Mud	Soil texture
Soil	7.68	3.42	600 gm/kg soil	188 gm/kg soil	152 gm/kg soil	Sandy mixture

Table 2. The Components of the Solution (Marvel)

Components	The ratio
Ozot N ₂ O	2%
Phosphorous pentoxide P ₂ O ₅	3%
Potassium oxide K ₂ O	15%
Chelated iron and a complementary set of amino acids	0.1%

Study Indications

The experiment included the following four treatments:

Nitrogen (% N)

Determination of nitrogen percentage: the nitrogen element was estimated according to the Keldal method using a device Micro-Kjeldal (Novozamsky et al.,1974).

Phosphorus (%P)

Phosphorus was estimated by Spectrophotometer at wave length 882 nm (Haynes, 1980).

Potassium (% K)

Which determination by flame meter (Wiessmann and K. Nehring,1989).

Iron and Zinc

The concentrations both of Fe, Zn (mg/gm dry matter) were estimated in the leaves using an atomic absorption spectro photometer according to the method mentioned in (Mousalli, 2000).

Results and Discussion

Leaves Content from Nitrogen (% N)

Table (3) shows that the significant effect of Marvel solution in concentration 2 ml/ l. (F2) on content of apricot leaves from nutrients, as the highest rate of nitrogen element in concentration 2 ml/l. (F2) was 2.091 % compared to the control treatment which gave the lowest rate it was 1.765%, as shown in Table (3). The

significant effect of antioxidants, as a citric acid at a concentration 1000 gm/l. gave the highest rate of 2.250%. Meanwhile, the concentration 1000 gm/l. from ascorbic acid was less concentrated and recorded 1.778%. This may be caused by a role of foliar fertilization, including the important nutrients in vital processes, as the nitrogen element is important to the plant because it is included in the composition of most of the significant vital substances of the plant such as proteins, enzymes and nucleic acids (DNA, RNA) (Singh, 2003).

As for the interaction Table (3) showed that the significant effect of foliar fertilization (Marvel) with antioxidants (ascorbic and citric acid) in the content of apricot leaves of the nitrogen element, as it gave an interaction treatment (2 ml/l. marvel + 1000 mg/l. citric acid) (F2*S2) was highest rate 2.253% compared with the control treatment (0 ml/l. marvel + 0 mg/l. antioxidants) (F1*Z) which gave the lowest rate reached 1.493%.

Table 3. Effect of Foliar Fertilizer (Marvel) and Antioxidants (Citric and Ascorbic Acid) on the Nitrogen Content in Apricot Tree Leaves

Antioxidants Marvel	Control T. Z 0 mg /L.	Ascorbic acid T. A1 500 mg/L.	Ascorbic acid T. A2 1000 mg/L.	Citric acid T S1 500 mg /L.	Citric acid T S2 1000 mg /L.	Rate of Marvel solution
F1 0 ml / L.	1.496	1.557	1.890	1.640	2.247	1.765
F2 2 ml / L.	2.123	2.290	1.667	2.120	2.253	2.091
Rate of antioxidants	1.808	1.923	1.778	1.880	2.250	
L.S.D 0.05	Marvel 0.255	antioxidants 0.403		interaction 0.570		

Leaves Content from Phosphorus (%P)

From Table (4) the significant effect is clear of Marvel solution at concentration 2 ml/l. (F2) on content of apricot leaves from nutrients, where the highest rate of phosphorus element in concentration 2 ml/ L. (F2) was 0.251 % while the control treatment which gave the lowest rate it was 0.241%, as shown in Table (4) the significant effect of antioxidants, as a citric acid at a concentration of 1000 mg/l. gave the highest rate of 0.275% while the control treatment gave the lowest rate it was 0.217% .

This may be caused by a role of phosphorus element in the process of carbon metabolism and the construction and breakdown of

carbohydrates and transfer energy. In addition, it is included in the composition of amino acids, energy-carrying compounds, and some enzymes (Jundia,2003).

While the interaction treatments Table (4) shows the significant effect of Marvel solution with antioxidants (ascorbic and citric acid) in the content of apricot leaves of the phosphorus element, as it gave an interaction treatment (0 ml/l. Marvel + 1000 mg/l. citric acid) (F1*S2) highest rate was 0.276% compared with control treatment (0 ml/l. Marvel + 0 mg/l. antioxidants) (F1*Z0) which gave the lowest rate 0.217%.

Table 4. Effect of Foliar Fertilizer (Marvel) and Antioxidants (Citric and Ascorbic Acid) on the Phosphorus Content in Apricot Tree Leaves

Antioxidants Marvel	Control T. Z 0 mg /L.	Ascorbic acid T. A1 500 mg/L.	Ascorbic acid T. A2 1000 mg/L.	Citric acid T S1 500 mg /L.	Citric acid T S2 1000 mg /L.	Rate of Marvel solution
F1 0 ml / L.	0.229	0.212	0.233	0.256	0.276	0.241
F2 2 ml / L.	0.205	0.267	0.263	0.247	0.274	0.251
Rate of antioxidants	0.217	0.239	0.248	0.251	0.275	

L.S.D	Marval	antioxidants	interaction
0.05	0.003	0.004	0.006

Leaves Content from Potassium (%K)

The significant effect is very clear from Table 5 of Marvel solution at concentration 2 ml/l. is the code given (F2) on content of apricot leaves from nutrients, where the highest rate of potassium element in concentration 2 ml/ L. (F2) was 1.999 % while the control treatment F1 which gave the lowest rate 1.643%, as shown in Table (5). The treatments of antioxidants have a significant effect, as a citric acid at a concentration of 1000 mg/l. gave the highest rate of 2.038% compared with ascorbic acid treatment A2, and control treatment Z0 those which gave the lowest rate they were 1.608%, 1.708% successively.

Perhaps the reason in this case revert to the role of foliar fertilizer which is very rich from micronutrients and its role in lots of physiologic process in to the plant such as transfer of salts of micronutrients and cell division (Obreza, 2003).

Further, the interaction treatments Table (5) shows the significant effect of Marvel solution with antioxidants (ascorbic and citric acid) in the content of apricot leaves of the potassium element, as it gave an interaction treatment (2 ml/l. Marvel + 1000 mg/l. ascorbic acid) (F2*A2) highest rate was 2.130% compared with the interaction treatments F1A2 and F1Z0 which gave the lowest rate that were 1.370%, 1.473% successively.

Table 5. Effect of Foliar Fertilizer (Marvel) and Antioxidants (Citric and Ascorbic Acid) on the Potassium Content in Apricot Tree Leaves

Antioxidants Marvel	Control T. Z 0 mg /L.	Ascorbic acid T. A1 500 mg/L.	Ascorbic acid T. A2 1000 mg/L.	Citric acid T S1 500 mg /L.	Citric acid T S2 1000 mg /L.	Rate of Marvel solution
F1 0 ml / L.	1.473	1.810	1.370	1.477	2.087	1.643
F2 2 ml / L.	1.943	2.130	1.847	2.083	1.990	1.999
Rate of antioxidants	1.708	1.970	1.608	1.780	2.038	
L.S.D	Marval	antioxidants		interaction		
0.05	0.114	0.180		0.255		

Leaves Content from Iron (Fe mg /l.)

From Table (6) it was found that the significant effect of concentration 2 ml/l. is the given code (F2) of Marvel solution on content of apricot leaves from nutrients. Where the highest rate of iron element in concentration 2 ml/l. (F2) was 12.33 mg/l. while the control treatment F1 which gave the lowest rate 11.58 mg/l, as shown in Table (6). The antioxidants treatment has a significant effect, as a citric acid at a concentration of 1000 mg /l. (S2) gave the rate 12.65 mg/l. compared with control treatment Z0 which gave the lowest rate 10.44 mg/l.

spraying with citric acid and nutrients on grapes, Red Globe cultivar where foliar spraying caused significant increase in most of the studied traits.

In addition, the interaction treatments Table (6) explains the significant effect of Marvel solution with antioxidants (ascorbic and citric acid) in the content of apricot leaves of the iron element, as it gave an interaction treatment (2 ml/L. Marvel + 1000 mg / L. ascorbic acid) (F2*A2) highest rate 13.40 mg/L. compared with interaction treatment F1Z0 which gave the lowest rate of 8.81 mg/L.

This is consistent with what (Haitham,2018) found when they studied the effect of foliar

Table 6. Effect the Foliar Fertilizer (Marvel) and Antioxidants (Citric and Ascorbic Acid) on Iron Content in Apricot Tree Leaves

Antioxidants Marvel	Control T. Z 0 mg /L.	Ascorbic acid T. A1 500 mg/L.	Ascorbic acid T. A2 1000 mg/L.	Citric acid T S1 500 mg /L.	Citric acid T S2 1000 mg /L.	Rate of Marvel solution
F1 0 ml / L.	8.81	12.11	12.25	11.59	13.13	11.58
F2 2 ml / L.	12.07	12.10	13.40	11.92	12.17	12.33
Rate of antioxidants	10.44	12.10	12.83	11.75	12.65	
L.S.D	Marval	antioxidants		interaction		
0.05	0.581	0.918		1.299		

Leaves Content from Zinc (Fe mg /l.)

The Table (7) shows the effect of foliar fertilization on the content of apricot leaves from zinc where it was concentration 2 ml/ L. is the given code (F2) of Marvel solution, where the highest rate of zinc element in concentration 2 ml/l (F2) was 26.72 mg/l. Compared with the control treatment F1 which gave the lowest rate it was 22.59 mg/l., as shown in Table (7). The antioxidants treatment has a significant effect but it wasn't a high increase, as citric acid at a concentration of 1000 mg/l. (S2) gave the rate of

27.58 mg/l. compared to control treatment Z0 that gave the lowest rate 21.82 mg/l.

The reason for this can be explained by the fact that citric acid can play the role of chelating substance for micronutrients that are sprayed on plants to facilitate their entry to the surface of the leaf to equalize the electric charge of leaf surfaces (Al-Rayes, 1980).

In addition to the interaction treatments between foliar fertilization and antioxidants, Table (7) indicated that there was no significant effect on the zinc content of leaves.

Table 7. Effect of Foliar Fertilizer (Marvel) and Antioxidants (Citric and Ascorbic Acid) on the Zinc Content in Apricot Tree Leaves

Antioxidants Marvel	Control T. Z 0 mg /L.	Ascorbic acid T. A1 500 mg/L.	Ascorbic acid T. A2 1000 mg/L.	Citric acid T S1 500 mg /L.	Citric acid T S2 1000 mg /L.	Rate of Marvel solution
F1 0 ml / L.	18.74	22.85	23.75	21.47	26.17	22.59
F2 2 ml / L.	24.90	27.03	24.79	27.87	28.99	26.72
Rate of antioxidants	21.82	24.94	24.27	24.67	27.58	
L.S.D	Marval	antioxidants		interaction		
0.05	1.979	3.129		N.S		

Conclusion

The nutrient solution F2 and antioxidant factor A2, S2 had the greatest influence on the mineral elements in apricot tree leaves (nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, zinc, and iron). The interactions between components F2*A2, F2*S2 (nutrient solution and antioxidants) produced the maximum mineral element content in apricot tree leaves (NPK, Fe and Zn).

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

References

- A.F.G. (2015). *Apricot farming information Guide*. India.
- Ahmed, F. F., & Morsy, M. H. (2001, March). Response of " Canino " apricot trees grown in the new reclaimed land to application of some nutrients and ascorbic acid. In *The fifth Arabian Hort. Conf. Ismalia, Egypt* (pp. 27-34).

- Ahmed, T. M. (2003). Education and national development in Nigeria. *Journal of studies in Education*, 10(1), 35-46.
- Al-Douri, A., & Al-Rawi, A. K. S. (2000). *Fruit production*. First edition, Dar Al-Kutub, University Mosul.
- Al-Muriqui, A. & Musa, J. (2005). *Chemistry of orchard plants*. Alexandria University press, Arab Republic of Egypt.
- Al-Rayes, A.H. (1980). *Plant Nutrition (part one and two)*. Dar Al-Kutub for Printing and publishing, university of Mosul.
- Álvarez-Fernández, A., Paniagua, P., Abadía, J., & Abadía, A. (2003). Effects of Fe deficiency chlorosis on yield and fruit quality in peach (*Prunus persica* L. Batsch). *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 51(19), 5738-5744. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf0344402c>
- Bortiri, E., Oh, S. H., Jiang, J., Baggett, S., Granger, A., Weeks, C., ... & Parfitt, D. E. (2001). Phylogeny and systematics of *Prunus* (Rosaceae) as determined by sequence analysis of ITS and the chloroplast trnL-trnF spacer DNA. *Systematic Botany*, 26(4), 797-807. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1043/0363-6445-26.4.797>
- Haitham, M.A.M. (2018). Effect sprayed citric acid macro and micronutrients on yield berries quality of Red Globe Grapevines. *Journal of horticulture science and ornamental plant*, 10(1), 53-59. <http://dx.doi.org/10.17660/ActaHortic.2002.594.21>
- Havlin, J. L., Beaton, J. D., Tisdale, S. L., & Nelson, W. L. (2005). *Soil Fertilizers*.
- Haynes, R. J. (1980). A comparison of two modified Kjeldahl digestion techniques for multi-element plant analysis with conventional wet and dry ashing methods. *Communications in Soil Science and Plant Analysis*, 11(5), 459-467. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00103628009367053>
- Johnson, J.R., Gish, F.N. & Andrews, P.K. (1999). Influence of ascorbic acid sprays on apple sunburn. *Good Fruit Grower*, 50, 13.
- Joley, L.E., Jaynes, R.A., & Knoxville, E.D. (1975). *Pistachio in handbook of North America Nut trees*. Northern Nut Growers Associ.
- Jundia, H. (2003). *Physiological of fruit trees*. Al-Dar Arab for publishing and distribution, Arab Republic of Egypt.
- Mousalli, H. A. (2000). *Apricot and cultivate it , its varieties, its pests and manufacture and preservation of its products*. First edition, Publications Dar Aladdin, Syria
- Novamsky, I., Eck, R.V., Schouwenburg, C., & Walinga, I. (1974). Total nitrogen determination in plant material by means of the indophenol-blue method. *Netherlands Journal of Agricultural Science*. 22, 3-5. <https://doi.org/10.18174/njas.v22i1.17230>
- Obreza, T. A. (2003). Importance of potassium in a Florida citrus nutrition program. *Better crops*, 87(1), 19-22.
- Obreza, T.A., Zekri, M. & Hanlon, E.W. (2008). Soil and leaf Tissue Teasting. In: *Nutrition of Florida Citrus Trees*, Obereza, T.A. and K.T. morgan (eds) 2nd. Florida Cooperative Extension Service, Institute of Food and Agriculture.
- Singh, A. (2003). *Fruit physiology and production*. 5th ed. Kalyani publishers New Delhi-110002.
- Taiz, L., & Zeiger, E. (2002). *Plant Physiology Sinauer*. Inc., Sunderland, MA.
- Vorobev, V.F. (1999). The keeping quality of apple when treated with antioxidant, Russia. *Sadorodstvo i Vingrodorstvo*, 2, 12-14.
- Wiessmann, H. & Nehring, K. (1989). *Agricultur chemische Untersuchum gsmethoden fuer Duengeund Futtermittel Boden und Milch Dritte vollig neubearbeitete Auflage*. Verlag Paul Parey Hamburg und, Berlin west Germany.
- Zulaikha. (2013). Effect ascorbic acid on many vegetative and fruit traits for trees Early coronet cultivar. *Journal of plant physiological*, 24(3), 1-15.